

An artistic illustration of a Mosasaur breaching the ocean surface. The Mosasaur is depicted in shades of green and blue, with its head and back above the water, creating a large splash. Two birds are shown in flight above the animal. Below the surface, the Mosasaur's tail and body are visible in the deep blue water, surrounded by several ammonites with colorful, spiral shells. The sky is a light blue with soft white clouds.

The Mosasaur

*The Journal of the
Delaware Valley
Paleontological
Society*

Volume X August 2018

*Zak Boley
2018*

The Mosasaur

The Journal of the Delaware Valley Paleontological Society

Editor

Jason Schein

Director, Bighorn Basin Paleontological Institute, P.O. Box 672, Red Lodge, MT, 59068, scheijp@gmail.com

Layout Editor

William J. Shankle

The Delaware Valley Paleontological Society, Inc., P.O. Box 686 Plymouth
Meeting, Pennsylvania 19462-0686, wjshankle@gmail.com

The Mosasaur is published on an occasional basis by the Delaware Valley Paleontological Society in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania. Copyright 2018 The Delaware Valley Paleontological Society, Inc. ISSN 0736-3907. DVPS P.O. Box 686, Plymouth Meeting, Pennsylvania 19462-0686.

Ordering information for additional copies of The Mosasaur is available at <http://www.dvps.org>

Editorial correspondence should be sent to the editor. The editorial policy of The Mosasaur appears inside on the next page of this issue. - First Printing – December 2018

COVER ART – Breaching Mosasaur - Illustration by Dr. Zack Boles of Rowan University.

REVIEW OF AN INVERTEBRATE FAUNA FROM THE WOODBURY FORMATION HADDONFIELD, NEW JERSEY, USA

SHANKLE, WILLIAM ^{1,2} JOHNSON, RALPH^{1,2}

¹ *Monmouth Amateur Paleontologists' Society, 57 Oceanport Ave., West Long Branch, NJ, 07764*

² *Delaware Valley Paleontology Society, PO Box 686, Plymouth Meeting, PA, 19462, dvpsnew@gmail.com*

ABSTRACT – This paper presents a revised interpretation of some important elements of an invertebrate fauna reported from the Woodbury formation at Haddonfield, NJ by Kuehne, Kuehne (2016). The erroneous taxonomic identification of the ammonites *Discoscaphities* sp., *Baculites ovatus* Say, 1820 and the exogyrine oyster species *Exogyra costata* Say, 1820 as occurring in the early Campanian Woodbury formation would incorrectly expand their stratigraphic ranges on the northern Atlantic Coastal Plain well beyond recognized limits and *Exogyra* zonation as defined by Stephenson (1914).

INTRODUCTION

An extensive invertebrate fauna was reported from the Woodbury formation exposed near the classic *Hadrosaurus foulkei* Leidy (1858) site in Haddonfield, New Jersey in W. Kuehne and A. Kuehne (2016). The paper provided a comprehensive faunal list along with lithographic and stratigraphic descriptions of the site based on the works of D. Kuehne (1993, 1999), Bernstein (1986), Weller (1907), Conard (1870) Lea (1861) and Foulke (1858). The work will serve as a valuable resource for understanding the depositional environment and biostratigraphy of this important site; however, we believe some of the specimen identifications were in error. The misidentification of the ammonite *Discoscaphities* sp., *Baculites ovatus* Say, 1820 and the the exogyrine oyster species *Exogyra costata* Say, 1820 as occurring in the lower Campanian Woodbury formation would incorrectly expand their ranges well beyond accepted limits and *Exogyra* zonation as defined by Stephenson (1914).

AMMONITE STRATIGRAPHIC RANGES

Throughout its range in North America the genus *Discoscaphities* has been found to be restricted to the upper Maastrichtian. In the northern Atlantic Coastal Plain, it occurs in the Tinton, New Egypt and Severn formations. Considering the rapid evolution rate of Uper Cretaceous scaphitids it is unlikely this genus would be found in the lower Campanian Woodbury formation.

Cobban (1969:6) established the existence of sexual dimorphism in scaphitid ammonites and the fact that the macroconchs specimens tend to be more inflated and robust. The microconchs (males) tend to be more slender with flattened flanks and enlarged ventral tubercles on the body chamber. In our opinion ANSP 80463 represents a crushed macroconch (female) specimen of *Scaphites hippocrepsis* DeKay, 1828. We also believe ANSP 80461, identified in W. Kuehne and A. Kuehne (2016) is a fragmentary microconch of the same species. *Scaphites hippocrepsis* DeKay, 1828 ranges from

the Merchantville up into the overlying Woodbury Formation.

On the Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain the range of *B. ovatus* Say, 1820 has been established in the literature as occurring in the upper late Campanian Mount Laurel formation and lower early Maastrichtian Navesink

formation. We believe ANSP 80429 is a specimen of *Baculites haresi* Reside, 1927. This species has a known range from the Merchantville formation up into the overlying Woodbury formation and is a much more likely candidate identification for a baculitid from the Haddonfield site. The flank ornament is also more indicative of *B. haresi* Reside, 1927.

Figure 1: Campanian and Maastrichtian stratigraphic units exposed in New Jersey, Delaware and Maryland. Courtesy of MAPS.

EXOGYRA ZONATION

Stephenson (1914) defined two broad biostratigraphic zones based on *Exogyra* occurrences in the study of the Cretaceous of the Atlantic Coastal Plain: the *Exogyra ponderosa* Roemer, 1852 zone and the *Exogyra costata* Say, 1820 zone. In the northern Atlantic Coastal Plain, Bernstein (1986:10) showed that the *Exogyra ponderosa* Roemer, 1849 zone encompasses the entire Matawan Group (Mount Laurel, Wenonah, Marshalltown, Englishtown, Woodbury and Merchantville Formations, see Figure 1). He correctly identified juvenile specimens from the Haddonfield as belonging to this species.

In the Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain the *Exogyra costata* Say, 1820 zone encompasses the Monmouth Group (Tinton, Red Bank, Navesink formations, see Figure 1). The earliest occurrence of *E. costata* Say, 1820 is in the upper most part of the Mount Laurel formation. W. Kuehne and A. Kuehne (2016) report that ANSP 80498 is a specimen of *Exogyra costata* var. *spinifera* Stephenson, 1914, which leads to the conclusion that the *E. costata* zone should be expanded down into the Matawan group.

The authors disagree with the identification of ANSP 80498 as a specimen of *Exogyra costata* var. *spinifera* Stephenson, 1914, but believe this is may be an undescribed dwarf species of *Exogyra* or a possible undescribed variety of *E. ponderosa* Roemer, 1852. In addition, the specimen in question is a juvenile which makes identification problematic. Adult exogyrine fossils are rare at Haddonfield making the collection of a diagnostic suite of specimens difficult.

Bernstein (1986:10) came to the similar conclusion stating:

“... the report by Richards and others (1958) of *E. costata* in the Woodbury Formation at Haddonfield in particular and in the Matawan Group as a whole is unprecedented and unsubstantiated. There is a lack of evidence to support identification of the *E. costata* anywhere in the Matawan Group, while there is evidence to the contrary. The report by Richards and others (1958) involved an error in taxonomic identification”

The following is a list of reported *E. costata* from the Woodbury formation which represent errors in taxonomic identification and could benefit from thorough review of this material.

Publications:

- Lea (1861:15)
- Richards (1958:117)
- Kuehne (1993:64)
- Kuehne, Kuehne (2016:44)

Specimens:

- ANSP 19338
- ANSP 55401
- ANSP 80498

FAUNAL IDENTIFICATIONS

Specimens whose identification were in error are listed in Figure 2 and those that have been synonymized are listed in Figure 3.

Specimen	Original Identification	Correct Identification
ANSP 80286	<i>Avellana costata</i> (Johnson, 1898)	<i>Acteon cretacea</i> Gabb, 1861
ANSP 80428	<i>Exogyra costata</i> var <i>spinifera</i> Stephenson, 1914	<i>Exogyra</i> sp.
ANSP 80429	<i>Baculites ovatus</i> Say, 1820	<i>Baculites haresi</i> Reeside, 1927
ANSP 80433	<i>Corbula</i> sp.	<i>Etea carolinensis</i> Conrad, 1875
ANSP 80463	<i>Discoscaphites</i> sp.	<i>Scaphites hippocrepsis</i> (DeKay, 1828)
ANSP 80466	<i>Legumen biplicata</i>	<i>Leptosolen biplicata</i> (Conard, 1858) Note: The incorrect Genus was a cleric error introduced in the editorial process.
ANSP 80472	<i>Pugnellus</i> sp.	<i>Hercorhynchus</i> sp.

Figure 2: Misidentified Specimens

Specimen	Original Identification	Current Synonym
ANSP 80427	<i>Protocallianassa mortoni</i> Pilsbury, 1901	<i>Mesostylus mortoni</i> (Pilsbury, 1901) by Schweitzer, Feldman 2012
ANSP 80440	<i>Nucula slackiana</i> (Gabb, 1860)	<i>Nucula percassa</i> Conrad, 1858 by Wingard, Sohl, (1990)
ANSP 80487	<i>Ostrea plumosa</i> Morton, 1833	<i>Striostrea plumose</i> (Morton, 1833) by ???Rindsberg (1998)
ANSP 80499	<i>Crassatellites linteus</i> (Conrad, 1860) Johnson, 1905	<i>Crassatella vadosa</i> Morton, 1834 by Wingard (1993)

Figure 3: Synonymized Specimen

REFERENCES

- Bernstein, M.R. 1986. Taxonomic and Stratigraphic Interpretation of Exogyrine Oysters (*Exogyra*, *Amphidonte*) in the Upper Cretaceous Woodbury Formation in Southern New Jersey. *Northeastern Geology* 8(1/2):4-12.
- Cobban, W.A. 1969. The Late Cretaceous Ammonites *Scaphites leei* Reeside and *Scaphites hippocrepsis* (DeKay) in the

- Western Interior of the United States. United States Geological Survey Professional Paper 619, 27 pp.
- Conard, 1858. Observations on a group of Cretaceous Fossil Shells, found in Tippah County, Mississippi, with descriptions of fifty-six new species. Journal of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia, Series 2, 3: 323-336.
- Conrad, 1860. Descriptions of New Species of Cretaceous and Eocene Fossils of Mississippi and Alabama. Journal of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia, Series 2, 4: 275-298.
- Conrad, 1870. Description of new fossil Mollusca principally Cretaceous. American Journal of Conchology 5: 96-103.
- Conard, 1875. Descriptions of new genera and species of fossil shells of North Carolina and in the Cabinet at Raleigh, etc., Appendix B, 28pp. *in* Kerr, W.C., Report of the Geological Survey of North Carolina: Geological Survey of North Carolina.
- DeKay, J.E. 1828. Report on several fossil multilocular shells from the State of Delaware: with observations on a second specimen of the new fossil genus *Eurypterus*. Annuals of the New York Lyceum, 2: 273-279.
- Foulke, W.P. 1858. On the fossil bones, shells and wood from Haddonfield. Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia 10:213-215,
- Gabb, W.M. 1861. Descriptions of new species of Cretaceous fossils from New Jersey, Alabama and Mississippi. Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia 13: 318-330.
- Kuehne, D. 1993. Further examination of the Woodbury and basal Englishtown Formations in Camden County and adjacent area, New Jersey. The Mosasaur 5: 59-62.
- Kuehne, D. 1999. Upper Cretaceous Macroinvertebrate Faunas of the Northern Atlantic Coastal Plain. The Mosasaur 6: 29-79.
- Kuehne, W.R. and Kuehne, A.J. 2016. Haddonfield, New Jersey – More than *Hadrosaurus foulkii*: Invertebrate Paleontology of the Site, The Mosasaur 9: 39-62.
- Johnson, C.W. 1898. New Cretaceous Fossils from an Artesian Well-Boring at Mount Laurel, N. J. Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia, 50: 461-464.
- Lea, I. 1861. Descriptions of New Fossil Mollusca, from the Cretaceous Formation at Haddonfield, New Jersey. Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia 1861, 13:143-150.
- Morton, 1834. Synopsis of the organic remains of the Cretaceous group of the United States. Illustrated by nineteen plates. Key and Biddle, Philadelphia, 88 pp. 19 pls.
- Pilsbury, H.A. 1901. Crustacea of the Cretaceous Formation of New Jersey. Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia, 53: 111-118.
- Reeside, J.B. 1927. The Cephalopods of the Eagle Sandstone and Related Formations

- in the Western Interior of the United States. United States Geological Survey Professional Paper 151, 87 pp.
- Richards, H.G., 1953. Record of the Rocks: The Geological Story of Eastern North America. The Ronald Press Company, New York, 413 pp.
- Richards, H.G., et. al. 1958. The Cretaceous Fossils of New Jersey, Part I: Porifera, Coelenterata, Annelida, Echinoidea, Brachiopoda and Pelecypoda: State of New Jersey, Department of Conservation and Economic Development. Trenton, NJ.
- Roemer, F.A. 1852. Die Kreidebildungen von Texas und ihre organischen Einschlusse, Adolph Marcus, Bonn, 100 pp.
- Say, T. 1820. Observations on some species of zoophytes, shells, etc., principally fossils. American Journal of Science, 2: 34-45.
- Scwhweitzer, C. E. and Feldman, R. M. 2011. New fossil Brachyura (Decapoda: Homoloidea, Dorippoidea, Carpilioidea) from the United Kingdom.
- Sohl, N.F. 1964. Neogastropoda, Opisthobranchia, and Basommatophora from the Ripley, Owl Creek, and Prairie Bluff Formations: Late Cretaceous Gastropods in Tennessee and Mississippi. United States Geological Survey Professional Paper 331-B, 344pp.
- Stephenson, L.W. 1914. Cretaceous deposits of the eastern Gulf region and species of *Exogyra* from the eastern Gulf region and the Carolinas. United States Geological Survey Professional Paper 81, 77pp.
- Weller, S. A. 1907. Report on the Cretaceous Paleontology of New Jersey. New Jersey Geological Survey, Paleontology Series, Vol. 4. Trenton: New Jersey Geological Survey.
- Wingard, G.L. 1993. A Detailed Taxonomy of Upper Cretaceous and Lower Tertiary Crassatellidae In Eastern North America: An Example of The Nature of Extinction. United States Geological Survey Professional Paper 1535, 131pps.
- Wingard, G. L, Sohl, N.F. 1990. Revision of the *Nucula percrassa* Conrad, 1858 Group in the Upper Cretaceous of the Gulf and Mid-Atlantic Coastal Plains: An Example of Bias the Nomenclature. Bulletin United States National Museum, No. 1535.